

**SPONTANEOUS MEMORY STRATEGIES IN A VIDEOGAME SIMULATING EVERYDAY
PROSPECTIVE MEMORY TASKS**

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Abstract

People can use different internal strategies to manage future intentions, but systematic research on these strategies and their significance for prospective memory (PM; remembering to perform planned intentions) performance is still quite sparse. In the present study, we examined self-reported internal strategy use with a 10-block version of the videogame EPELI in a group of 202 neurotypical adults of 18 to 50 years of age. In the game, the participants perform lists of everyday tasks from memory while navigating in a virtual apartment. Open-ended strategy reports were collected after each EPELI task block, and for comparison also after an EPELI Instruction Recall task and a Word List Learning task assessing episodic memory. On average 45% of the participants reported using some strategy in EPELI, the most common types being grouping, utilizing a familiar action schema, and condensing information. Our pre-registered hypothesis on the beneficial effect of self-initiated strategy use gained support, as strategy users showed better PM performance on EPELI as compared to no strategy users. Grouping could be identified as a clearly effective strategy type. Block-by-block transitions suggested gradual stabilization of strategy use over the 10 EPELI blocks. The proneness to use strategies showed a weak but reliable association between EPELI and Word List Learning. Overall, the present results highlight the importance of internal strategy use for understanding individual differences in PM performance, as well as the potential benefit for internal strategy employment when faced with everyday PM tasks.

1. Introduction

The use of different mnemonic strategies has a very long history (Yates, 1966) and extensive research evidence indicates that strategy employment can boost one's memory performance (for an overview, see e.g. Bellezza, 1981). The study of memory strategies is thus important for understanding the cognitive processes involved in task performance and the sources of inter- and intra-individual differences in task outcomes. Task features can have strong effects on spontaneous strategy use (e.g., Morrison et al., 2016), calling for the study of strategic behaviour in different task paradigms. Here we examined adults' spontaneous strategy use and its relationship with objective task performance in a new videogame designed to tap goal-directed behaviour and one of its aspects, prospective memory (PM; remembering to perform an action at some future point in time; McDaniel & Einstein, 2011), in life-like everyday contexts (Jylkkä et al., 2022, Preprint; see also Seesjärvi et al. 2022). The present study was expected to shed light on adults' self-generated PM strategies and their significance for actual PM performance, an issue that has not received much systematic research.

We focused on internal, self-generated memory strategies in a task where the use of external memory aids was prohibited. We operationalize these internal strategies as conscious, verbalizable ways to solve a memory task. A number of studies have addressed strategy employment in episodic or working memory, either by examining spontaneous strategy use (McNamara & Scott, 2001; Turley-Ames & Whitfield, 2003; Dunlosky & Kane, 2007; Dunning & Holmes, 2014; Laine et al., 2018; Fellman et al., 2020; Forsberg et al., 2020; Malinovitch et al., 2021; Waris, Fellman, et al., 2021; Waris, Jylkkä, et al. 2021) or by seeking causal evidence for the role of strategies in memory performance through manipulation of participants' strategic choice (e.g., McNamara & Scott, 2001; Turley-Ames & Whitfield, 2003; Carretti et al., 2007; Bailey et al., 2014; Borella et al., 2017; Laine et al., 2018; Fellman et al., 2020; Forsberg et al., 2020; Malinovitch et al., 2021). In both cases, enhancements in memory performance have been repeatedly observed, albeit the degree and duration of these effects has varied.

In PM research, the relevance of the study of strategy use has also been recognized, and metacognitive processes, responsible for strategy generation, task initiation and monitoring (Chein & Schneider, 2012), are thought to guide the way a PM task is tackled (e.g., Rummel

& Meiser, 2013). While some strategic aspects of PM behaviour are observable either indirectly (resource allocation to an ongoing non-PM task) or directly (monitoring through clock-checking in time-based PM tasks), many internal strategies are accessible only through self-reports. As internal strategies are at the focus of the current study, we will briefly review here previous research that has addressed self-generated and self-reported PM internal strategy use. This rather limited literature entails imaginary everyday PM situations, laboratory PM tasks, and daily life.

With regard to imaginary everyday memory scenarios, Intons-Peterson and Fournier (1986) examined university undergraduates' spontaneous internal and external strategy choices in different imaginary situations. Both the imaginary situations (e.g., "You are going to begin a two-day trip tomorrow to visit a place you have never seen before. You look at a map for directions. What would you do to try to remember where to go if you couldn't take the map with you?") and possible strategy types were provided to the participants. For PM situations, internal and external strategy use was proposed by 23.9% and 25.2% of the participants, respectively. The participants' strategy choices were also influenced by the PM task at hand (verbal vs. spatial). Across all the past and future imaginary situations, the most commonly chosen internal strategies were mental rehearsing (13.0%) and mental retracing (thinking about something that happened before, or that may happen, step by step, in an attempt to remember something; 11.9%). A more recent related study by Penningroth and Scott (2013) employed an imaginary PM task to elicit open-ended strategy reports from their undergraduate participants. While external strategies were clearly most frequent (the use of note, timer, or calendar appeared in 12-53% of the reports), one internal strategy, mental rehearsal, was listed by ca 3% of their participants.

Another line of research has employed questionnaires to probe everyday strategy use in highly relevant PM tasks such as taking one's medication. Gould et al. (1997) probed medication adherence in older adults and identified several common ways participants used in remembering to take one's medicine. These included associating pill-taking with certain regular daily activities, mentally repeating the instructions, and concentrating hard on the information related to medicine intake. Another survey on medication adherence by Blaskewicz Boron et al. (2013) indicated that 43% of their elderly responders employed

either external or internal strategies for remembering to take their medication. Two of the seven strategy alternatives provided to the participants could be considered as internal, namely association (using an activity or event to help in remembering to take medication) and planning (thinking ahead about when one will take medication). Of the strategy users, 40% and 23% reported employing association and planning, respectively.

Finally, strategy use has been probed in conjunction with PM experiments. Reese-Melancon et al. (2019) examined self-reported strategies in event-based laboratory PM tasks. Their study indicated that half of the participants reported strategy employment. By far the most common strategies were continuous silent rehearsal of the PM task and consciously keeping up a sensory-motor readiness to perform the PM part of the task (e.g., tapping the finger over the PM-related response button). Reese-Melancon et al. (op.cit.) did also address the important link between strategy use and actual PM performance, finding that self-reported strategy use was associated with a significantly better performance on the more demanding task condition (a nonfocal event-based PM task).

The studies cited above suggest that part of adults use self-generated internal memory strategies to remember future actions, but depending on task settings, their type and frequency show considerable variation that prompts further research. More importantly, their relationships with objectively measured PM performance have received only limited attention (see Reese-Melancon et al., 2019, for an exception).

In contrast to the rather few studies on self-generated strategy use in PM, several intervention studies have examined the effects of PM strategy training on task performance. A recent meta-analysis by Jones et al. (2021) demonstrated the efficacy of such training regimes. The most frequently taught strategy has been implementation intention (creating an environmental cue for an intention and speaking it aloud: “If I see cue X, I’ll perform Y”). Other PM strategy training regimes have included a visual imagery strategy (imagining oneself performing Y when seeing cue X), spaced retrieval (recall of information over progressively longer periods of time), increased self-reflection (“Am I forgetting anything?”), or a combination of multiple strategies. While these intervention studies have consistently documented the facilitative effects of strategy use on PM performance and thus provided

important causal evidence for the role of strategies in PM performance, they do not address spontaneous strategy use that is relevant for understanding individual differences in PM performances. Moreover, Jones et al. (2021) noted that the ecological validity of the PM assessments employed has been low¹. Thus, to clarify PM strategy use in more life-like contexts, further research with new paradigms is called for.

EPELI (Executive Performance in Everyday Living) is a recently developed videogaming task where participants move around in a virtual apartment, performing a list of common household tasks (e.g., preparing food, cleaning the place, getting ready to go to a hobby) orally given by an avatar. It provides a rich yet controllable context for quantitative measurement of goal-directed behaviour and PM in a more life-like setting. The first study with EPELI, conducted with school-age children, found that it differentiated children with ADHD diagnosis from neurotypical controls, and that efficacy on EPELI game play correlated with parent-rated executive problems and ADHD symptoms (Seesjärvi et al., 2022). Compared to classical laboratory paradigms, the more naturalistic situations and the freedom to choose one's actions in EPELI provide an innovative and ecologically more relevant way to examine spontaneous PM strategy use and its relationship with actual task performance. This inquiry is also relevant in terms of potential interventions: recognizing and facilitating self-generated strategy use can provide a particularly effective avenue for cognitive training (e.g., Scarff et al., 2022). In the present online study, we employed a 10-block flat screen adult version of EPELI and collected open-ended strategy reports from the participants after each block.

The present pre-registered study (<https://osf.io/m7c9a>; "Study 2") set one a priori hypothesis and two research questions. Based on the extensive evidence for the facilitative role of strategies in episodic and working memory performance (see above), our hypothesis was that EPELI performance shows a positive association with spontaneous strategy use. The first research question addressed the possible evolvment of strategy use over the 10 EPELI task blocks. Earlier research has indicated a rapid stabilization of the use of mnemonic strategies (Waris, Fellman, et al., 2021; Waris, Jylkkä, et al. 2021), but that evidence comes

¹Jones et al. (2021) employed the following criteria for ecological validity ratings of PM assessments: did the assessment employ a delayed-intention task rather than merely a self-report, did it take place outside the laboratory setting, did one include participant-generated tasks based on participants' personal daily activities.

from experimental working memory and episodic memory tasks. A similar involvement in EPELI would speak for its generality, as one would expect within the cognitive skill learning framework (Chein & Schneider, 2012). The second research question concerned the congruity of participants' strategy use vs. non-use in EPELI and two other memory tasks (EPELI Instruction Recall task, Word List Learning task). Strategy use appears to vary widely even within a memory domain (Morrison et al., 2016), and it is not clear to what extent individuals could be characterized by strategy proneness, i.e., the degree to which they tend to resort to strategies when faced with different memory tasks. Elucidation of commonly used mnemonic strategies and their involvement within the EPELI task may increase our understanding of the underlying mechanisms of complex PM performance. Ultimately, this has the potential to inform the development of personalized strategy instructions that could be used in real life by people suffering from PM problems.

2. Methods

2.1. Participants

Research ethics screening was conducted by the Ethics Board of the Departments of Psychology and Logopedics at the Åbo Akademi University, Turku, Finland. Anonymous participants were recruited on the crowdsourcing site Prolific (prolific.co), targeting both neurotypical participants and adults with diagnosed ADHD (both groups of age 18-50, currently living in the UK, first language English). They received monetary compensation for their participation. Here we focus only on the neurotypical controls and their strategy use in EPELI. The rest of the data, including both questionnaires and other cognitive tasks (see Jylkkä et al., 2022, Preprint), will be reported in separate papers.

The data collection in August - December 2021 proceeded in three stages, two prescreens and the study proper that encompassed five sessions on five separate days (see Jylkkä et al., 2022, Preprint, for further details). The purpose of the very short first prescreen was to identify a sufficiently large sample of adults with ADHD. Altogether 12 446 participants answered whether they had ADHD/ADD diagnosis and filled out part A of the Adult ADHD Self-Report Scale (Adler et al., 2006). A total of 1 517 participants were invited for the second prescreening that surveyed the following information: basic demographics (age,

gender, income, education); medical history (e.g., diagnosis of neurological illness, severe depression, bipolar disorder, psychosis, or schizophrenia); eyesight and color vision; alcohol use with AUDIT questions 1-3; nicotine use; and use of other psychoactive substances. Moreover, they filled out ASRS part B to further assess ADHD problems, DSM-5 Self-Rated Level 1 Cross-Cutting Symptom Measure—Adult (Bravo et al., 2018) to assess overall mental health on several dimensions, and some further questionnaires. The second prescreen took circa 10 minutes.

An invitation to the experiment proper was sent only to participants who fulfilled the following criteria: normal or corrected-to-normal vision; no color blindness; no neurodevelopmental disorders; no neurological illness that affects the participant's current life; never diagnosed with severe depression, bipolar disorder, psychosis, or schizophrenia across the lifespan; and no self-reported substance-abuse problem. Moreover, the following eligibility criteria based on the DSM Symptom Measure were applied: no reported suicidality (i.e., score 0 in item 11), and sum scores of less than 3 in the depression, mania, and anxiety domains (i.e., at most "mild" symptoms, or a response indicating occurrence of the symptom not more than during "several days" over the last two weeks). After considering all inclusion and exclusion criteria and missing values in our strategy and performance variables on EPELI (we performed listwise exclusions, meaning that participants having 1 or more missing values were excluded), as well as univariate outlier screenings (scoring three times the interquartile range above or below the 1st or the 3rd quartile in a given outcome variable), the final sample size of the control group was 202. The mean age was 32 years, and 71% of the participants were females.

2.2. Test sessions

The experiment proper encompassed five sessions. EPELI was always administered in the first session and the diary questions (see below) were administered in every session, while the other tasks were fully counterbalanced between the participants, randomly allocating them into one of the four counterbalanced task sets. The five testing sessions were performed on separate weekdays with at least a 12-hour interval in-between, and all sessions were to be completed within 14 days. Each session took approximately 40 minutes,

and the complete duration of testing was circa 3 hours and 20 minutes. Only those participants who completed EPELI in their first session were allowed to partake in the other sessions.

2.3. The EPELI game

The EPELI game started with guided hearing threshold detection that adjusted the sound volume levels to equal level across all participants, after which the participants found themselves in the lobby of a virtual apartment. A virtual character named Vincent, appeared in front of the participants, welcoming them and giving instructions to the game. This was followed by a practice session where participants had to move an apple from one room to another. Visual field of view in the game was controlled by mouse and a crosshair was visible at the center of the screen. The participants moved around the apartment by clicking on white circles on the floor, and they were able to move directly to any visible circle. A clock with running time (reset at the beginning of each block) was available in the lower right corner by clicking the right mouse button. Objects could be grabbed and laid on surfaces by clicking on them. Several of the objects were interactable, for example, closets that could be opened, toys scattered on the floor that could be manipulated, or the piano in the living room that one could play. See Figure 1 for still images of the EPELI game.

Figure 1. The EPELI game. The participant is to perform everyday chores from memory in a virtual apartment. The floorplan (A) is not available to the participant. The list of tasks for each block is given orally by the virtual character Vincent (B). In this game version, the event-based PM task is to place the teddy bear, when present amongst the toys scattered on the floor, on the sofa (C). The participant moves around by clicking on white hotspots on the floor. A clock with running time can be opened by clicking the right mouse button.

The present adult version of EPELI contained 10 blocks with eight tasks per block. In the beginning of each block, Vincent orally introduced a theme (e.g., “You have invited your friend to dinner. You are sitting on your bed. Listen carefully to the things you should do in the apartment. They are as follows.”) and gave a list of 7-8 everyday tasks. Three types of PM tasks appeared in Vincent’s block-wise instructions. Most of the tasks (altogether 70) were labelled as *free tasks* that did not have any specified trigger event or time point (seven per block; e.g., “Pick up the salad from the fridge and bring it to the dining table”, “Switch

on the table lamp on the work desk"). Five tasks were *time-based PM tasks* (to be performed at a given time point, e.g., "After one minute, warm up briefly with the exercise bike in the study"). These appeared in five blocks, (i.e., one per block), but never together with the event-based task that is described next. The *event-based PM task* was ongoing throughout the EPELI session, to be performed whenever a cue was present. The cue was a teddy bear, which was to be put on the sofa. The teddy was present in five of the 10 blocks (the ones that did not include a time-based PM task), located amongst toys scattered on the floor (see Figure 1C). The instruction to this event-based task was given by Vincent only once before the first block started. Hence, the task lists for the blocks did not include the event-based instruction anymore. Each block thus contained seven free tasks, and additionally either one time-based task or one event-based task, making in total eight tasks in each block. Sixty of the free tasks were in line with the general schema of the task block that was provided by Vincent, while ten of the free tasks (one per block) were non-schema-based, i.e., unrelated to the schema in question (e.g., during preparation of a vegetable soup, one had to run a bath). This was done to reduce predictability of the task lists.

In the present study, we employed three previously defined EPELI outcome variables, namely Total score, Task efficacy, and Navigation efficacy (see Seesjärvi et al., 2022). For each block, Total score depicts the number of correctly performed subtasks, Task efficacy corresponds to the proportion of relevant actions out of all actions (excluding clicks on the waypoints that enable moving around in the environment; 'relevant' means actions that contribute to completing the given tasks), and Navigation efficacy is the Total score divided by covered distance. These three variables were chosen here as they reflect overall performance on a block and because higher scores on these three variables unequivocally reflect better performance, enabling us to test the preregistered hypothesis that strategy use is associated with better success in EPELI.

After each block, the participants provided a written response to the following open question: "Please describe in as much detail as possible how you solved the previous set of tasks." These responses were used to code individual block-wise strategy use in EPELI, as described below. For studying the associations of strategy use between EPELI and the other two memory tasks (Word List Learning and EPELI Instruction Recall, described below), we also coded for each of the three tasks the number of blocks where a participant reported

strategy use (0-10 for the 10-block EPELI, 0-3 for the 3-block Word List Learning, 0-1 for the single-block EPELI Instruction Recall).

2.4. Word List Learning task

This episodic memory/learning task was adopted from Waris, Fellman, et al. (2021). It consisted of a list of 18 common nouns that was presented three times in randomized order. After each presentation, the participants were to recall as many words as possible. Each word was shown on the screen for 1 second, separated by a 1-second blank-screen interval. After the final word in a list had been shown, a multiple-choice distractor task appeared. The distractors were arithmetical tasks (e.g., $9 + 8 - 7 + 6 = ?$) to wash out the words from working memory.

After the distractor task, the participants were to type in the words in any order in a set of 18 boxes. Words had to be typed correctly, but non-letter characters or spaces were permitted before or after the word. The dependent measure was the number of correctly recalled words per list.

After each of the three word list presentations, the participants gave a written response to the following question: "Please describe in as much detail as possible how you solved the previous word list task (not the math task). That is, how did you try to memorize the words?". The responses were used for coding their strategies (see 2.6.).

2.5. EPELI Instruction Recall task

In this task, the participants received a list of 8 instructions (e.g., "Take off your overcoat and hang it in the coat rack") similar to the ones they had to memorize in the EPELI blocks. The instructions were presented one at a time on the computer screen, for the duration of four seconds each. The theme of the list was "Returning home from a grocery store". Immediately after being presented with the list, the participants were to write down as many instructions as they remembered. All elements in each instruction (e.g., "take off your overcoat" and "put it in the coatrack") had to be reported correctly to receive points. The dependent variable was the total number of correctly recalled instructions (0-8). Right after

the Instruction Recall task, the participant responded to the following open question: "Please describe in as much detail as possible how you solved the task. That is, how did you try to memorize the instructions?" The responses were used for coding the participants' strategies on this task (see 2.6.).

2.6. Strategy coding for the memory tasks

Based on our earlier work on the classification of open-ended memory strategy reports (Laine et al., 2018; Fellman et al., 2020; Waris, Fellman, et al., 2021; Waris, Jylkkä, et al. 2021), as well as expectations concerning PM-related strategies, we devised a coding scheme that is depicted in Supplementary Table 1. Two independent raters (ML, TE) coded each open-ended strategy response. For each participant, there were 10 strategy reports for EPELI (i.e., after each block). The raters coded each strategy report on three variables: the first reported strategy type, the total number of strategy types reported, and the total number of specific strategy details given (be they for one or more strategy types). Interrater agreement for the strategy coding in EPELI was assessed by unweighted kappa (κ) for the first reported strategy type and with linearly weighted kappa (κ_w) for the other two strategy variables (total number of strategy types reported, total number of specific strategy details). The data for these analyses comprised of all participants except for the initial batch of 20 subjects that was used for coding practice. The kappa coefficients for EPELI suggested substantial agreement between the two raters: κ 0.76 for the first reported strategy type, κ_w 0.75 for the total number of strategy types, and κ_w 0.73 for total number of specific strategy details. Differences in coding were solved by subsequent consensus meetings.

2.7. Bayesian statistical analysis

All statistical analyses were performed with R version 4.0.0 using the "BayesFactor" package (Morey & Rouder, 2015), and with JASP (version 0.16.3). Our Bayesian statistical analyses applied the default prior setting, that is, Cauchy distribution using a scaling factor $r = .707$. Bayes Factor (BF) allows for the assessment of the evidence for the null hypothesis or for the alternative hypothesis on a continuous scale with a range of $1 - \infty$. $BF = 1$ indicates

perfect ambiguity (no evidence for neither hypothesis), whereas a BF above or below 1 indicates evidence for the alternative or null hypothesis, respectively. Interpretation of the BFs followed the guidelines put forth by Kass and Raftery (1995), where BFs between 1-3 constitute “weak evidence”, BFs between 3-20 as “positive evidence”, BFs between 20-150 as “strong evidence”, and BFs > 150 as “very strong evidence”. Together with BFs, we also report estimates of between-group mean differences using a posterior distribution with 10 000 iterations coupled with their 95% credible intervals.

To test the hypothesis on the relationship between strategy use and the EPELI performance variables, we employed Bayesian Linear Mixed Effect models (LMEs) with strategy use (dichotomised as yes/no) and block as independent variables, and participant as a random factor on the intercept. This analytical approach made it possible to utilize the whole EPELI data set where the same participants could be strategy users and strategy non-users in different task blocks.

3. Results

3.1. Descriptive data on strategy use in EPELI

Mean performance on the five EPELI main variables is listed in Supplementary Table 2. Primary strategy type in the 10 EPELI task blocks is depicted in Figure 1A. It indicates that on average 45% of the participants reported spontaneous strategy use in the task blocks. The relative proportions of the primary strategy types varied somewhat between the blocks, with the most common ones being grouping, condensing information, and action schema utilization. Strategy users’ reports revealed most often the employment of a single strategy in a given block, rather than having multiple strategies in use (Figure 1B). With regard to the number of specific strategy details, Figure 1C shows that strategy users’ reports included most often no specific details (e.g., “I did the tasks room by room”).

Figure 2. Block-wise distributions of the three strategy-related variables in EPELI. Please see the online version for coloured figures.

A. Distribution of primary strategy type per block

Note. For each block, case counts and percentages are provided only for the categories with four or more cases.

B. The number of strategy types per block among those using a strategy in that block.

Note. For each block, case counts and percentages are provided only for the categories with four or more cases.

C. Distribution of the reported number of strategy details per block among those using a strategy in that block.

Note. For each block, case counts and percentages are provided only for the categories with four or more cases.

3.2. Testing the pre-registered hypothesis: strategy use is related to performance in EPELI

With the *Total score* as the outcome variable (Figure 3A), the BF showed very strong evidence of a main effect of strategy ($M_{diff} = -0.65$ 95 % HDI [-0.72 – -0.57] $BF_{H1} > 150 \pm 2.54\%$), indicating higher rates of completed subtasks for those using a strategy. Evidence for a main effect of block was weak ($M_{diff} = 0.02$ 95 % HDI [0.00 – -0.04] $BF_{H1} = 1.67 \pm 3.02\%$), showing that block-by-block performance as measured by the Total score did not change. Finally, there was weak evidence against a strategy x block interaction ($M_{diff} = 0.04$ 95 % HDI [0.02 – 0.06] $BF_{H1} = 1/2.17 \pm 2.53\%$).

With *Task efficacy* as the outcome variable (Figure 3B), we observed again very strong evidence for a main effect of strategy ($M_{diff} = -0.05$ 95 % HDI [-0.06 – -0.04] $BF_{H1} > 150 \pm 2.77\%$), favouring strategy users. Moreover, there was very strong evidence for a main effect of block ($M_{diff} = 0.01$ 95 % HDI [0.00 – 0.01] $BF_{H1} > 150 \pm 2.24\%$), reflecting considerable variability between the blocks, with the first block eliciting clearly lowest

scores. The evidence for an interaction between strategy and block favoured the null hypothesis with weak evidence ($M_{diff} = 0.00$ 95 % HDI [0.00 – 0.01] $BF_{H1} = 1/1.62 \pm 2.34\%$).

As regards *Navigation efficacy* (Figure 3C), there was very strong evidence for a main effect of strategy ($M_{diff} = -0.01$ 95 % HDI [-0.01 – -0.01] $BF_{H1} > 150 \pm 2.54\%$), with strategy users exhibiting higher scores. Very strong evidence for a main effect of block ($M_{diff} = 0.00$ 95 % HDI [0.00 – 0.00] $BF_{H1} > 150 \pm 5.43\%$) indicated considerable block-by-block variability. We found positive evidence against strategy use x block interaction ($M_{diff} = 0.00$ 95 % HDI [0.00 – 0.00] $BF_{H1} = 1/10 \pm 3.44\%$).

Figure 3. Block-by-block performance in the outcome variables (A) Total score, (B) Task efficacy, and (C) Navigation efficacy for strategy users vs. non-users in a given block ($n = 202$). Error bars represent 95% confidence intervals.

As additional analyses, we performed Bayesian LMEs for elucidating whether a specific primary strategy type or types was associated with the EPELI performance advantages. Because very few participants kept using a single strategy across the task blocks, this analysis was conducted on block-wise use of strategy types in each block, while participant was, as before, treated as a random factor on the intercept. Using pairwise contrasts, “no explicit strategy use” served as the baseline level in the independent variable, whereas a given strategy type served as the other level to which the former one was contrasted. Given

that many of the strategies were reported in only few instances, we defined a threshold, stipulating that a given strategy had to be reported in ≥ 10 instances in each block for being eligible for this analysis. Two strategy types reached this threshold, namely grouping (block with fewest instances $n = 17$) and condensing information (block with fewest instances $n = 10$).

The results depicted in Figure 4 showed very strong evidence for grouping strategy, as compared to no strategy use, being advantageous concerning Total score ($M_{\text{diff}} = 0.79$ 95 % HDI [0.68 – 0.88] $BF_{H1} > 150 \pm 2.83\%$), Task efficacy ($M_{\text{diff}} = 0.06$ 95 % HDI [0.05 – 0.08] $BF_{H1} > 150 \pm 4.67\%$), and Navigation efficacy ($M_{\text{diff}} = 0.01$ 95 % HDI [0.01 – 0.01] $BF_{H1} > 150 \pm 1.91\%$). This was not the case for condensing information; the results here showed moderate evidence against an effect of strategy type on each EPELI performance measure Total score ($M_{\text{diff}} = 0.23$ 95 % HDI [0.07 – 0.38] $BF_{H1} = 1/3.03 \pm 2.18\%$); Task efficacy ($M_{\text{diff}} = -0.01$ 95 % HDI [-0.02 – 0.01] $BF_{H1} = 1/11.11 \pm 5.88\%$); Navigation efficacy ($M_{\text{diff}} = 0.00$ 95 % HDI [0.00 – -0.00] $BF_{H1} = 1/11.11 \pm 4.53\%$). Evidence against a strategy type \times block interaction was either weak or positive for both grouping and condensing information on each of the three dependent variables (BF_{H1} range 1/10.00 to 1/1.15). All in all, our results indicate that grouping, but not condensing information, was linked to higher EPELI performance as compared to no strategy use.

Figure 4. Block-by-block performance on the outcome variables (A) Total score, (B) Task efficacy, and (C) Navigation efficacy for strategy non-users, grouping strategy users, and those using the strategy of condensing information. Note that the constellations of participants vary between the blocks, as a given participant can belong to different strategy categories in different blocks. Error bars represent 95 % confidence intervals.

3.3. Research question: does strategy use evolve during the 10 EPELI task blocks?

Figure 2 does not reveal any evident trends in the primary types of strategies employed over the 10 blocks. However, as shown in Figure 5, block transitions in strategy use indicate that the number of participants relying on the same strategy as in a previous block doubled during the first five block transitions. There were concomitant downward trends in strategy pickers (going from no strategy to some strategy) and strategy changers (going from one active strategy to another active strategy) over the block transitions. Overall, this descriptive pattern suggests a gradual stabilization in strategy use as the participants were becoming more familiar with EPELI. At the same time, over the whole task period a substantial proportion of participants remained strategy non-users when moving from one block to another.

Figure 5. Changes in strategy use over the 10 EPELI task blocks. Number of observations (individuals) shown for each of the 9 block transitions.

3.4. Research question: is there congruity in participants' strategy use over the three memory tasks?

The strategy use intercorrelations with the corresponding BFs are reported in Table 1. The results yielded positive evidence for an association in strategy use between EPELI and Word List Learning ($r=.212$, $BF_{10}=3.97$), so that more frequent use of a strategy in EPELI is related to more common strategy employment in Word List Learning as well. However, the proportion of shared variance is quite low (4.5%). Strategy use in the EPELI Instruction Recall task was not associated with strategy use in the other two memory tasks, but it should be noted that the task may have been less sensitive as it consisted of only a single block.

Table 1. Intercorrelations (Pearson's r) and corresponding Bayes factors (BF_{10}) of strategy use in EPELI, EPELI Instruction Recall, and Word List Learning. Strategy use defined as the number of task blocks where a participant reported employing a strategy.

Variable	EPELI	EPELI Instruction Recall
EPELI Instruction Recall	$r=0.178$	

	BF ₁₀ =1.45	
	n=173	
Word List Learning	r=0.212	r=0.067
	BF ₁₀ =3.97	BF ₁₀ =0.14
	n=166	n=166

4. Discussion

The aim of this study was to examine spontaneous use of internal strategies in adults when they were performing common daily chores from memory in a virtual setting. The analyses were expected to shed light on the employment of self-generated strategies in PM tasks similar to future intentions met in real life. More specifically, we tested the hypothesis that spontaneous strategy use is associated with better performance in the EPELI game.

Moreover, we explored the possible development of strategy use over the 10 task blocks, and congruity in strategy use over three different memory tasks. The results provided clear support for our pre-registered hypothesis, as strategy use compared to non-use was associated with better EPELI performance. With regard to the two additional research questions, strategy use appeared to evolve gradually over the task blocks as strategy changes became less common, and we saw some (rather weak) congruity in the tendency to employ a strategy in EPELI and in an episodic memory task, Word List Learning.

The present very strong evidence ($BF_{H1} > 150$) for a better outcome on the three EPELI performance measures for strategy users than non-users is in line with similar results obtained from the episodic memory and working memory domains (McNamara & Scott, 2001; Turley-Ames & Whitfield, 2003; Dunlosky & Kane, 2007; Dunning & Holmes, 2014; Laine et al., 2018; Fellman et al., 2020; Forsberg et al., 2020; Malinovitch et al., 2021; Waris, Fellman, et al., 2021; Waris, Jylkkä, et al. 2021), as well as laboratory PM tasks (Reese-Melancon et al. (2019). Indeed, both episodic memory and working memory, as well as executive functions, are considered to be central cognitive components underlying PM

(McDaniel & Einstein, 2011; Zuber & Kliegel, 2020). The present results serve to expand the findings on the positive link between strategy use and memory task performance, as EPELI more closely mimics real-life conditions compared to classical experimental PM tasks. Also in contrast to classical PM tasks, it represents a mixture of “shopping list” type tasks, time-based tasks, and event-based tasks, with the first category being by far the most common task type. Moreover, implementation of intentions followed right after the instructions. One could assume that part of the EPELI instructions remained in working memory, but as each block included 7-8 different tasks, EPELI is likely a supra-span memory task (i.e., partially dependent on episodic memory). The engagement of both working memory and episodic memory in EPELI does not necessarily affect the present strategy-related findings, as both memory systems should benefit from very similar strategies that either help to strengthen the memory trace (e.g., rehearsal/repetition), decrease the memory load by clustering the to-be-remembered actions into fewer units (grouping, condensing information), or link them to existing relevant long-term memory representations (e.g., action schema utilization).

As regards to specific primary strategies, their varying block-wise distributions and insufficient rates of observations limited the exploration of possible performance differences to three strategy types, namely no strategy (serving as baseline), grouping and condensing information. We obtained very strong evidence ($BF_{H1} > 150$) for users of grouping strategy, but not those with condensing information, performing better on the three EPELI measures than strategy non-users. Thus, these results highlight one particular strategy that appear to be well applicable and clearly useful in implementing intentions in the complex EPELI contexts. It is also interesting to note that besides grouping, the most common primary strategy types were condensing information and action schema utilization. These strategies differ markedly from the by far most common strategies (silent rehearsal, keeping up a sensory-motor readiness to perform the PM task) reported by Reese-Melancon et al. (2019) in a laboratory PM task. This discrepancy prompted us to examine the use of rehearsal/repetition in EPELI Instruction Recall: its proportion in the whole control group turned out to be 15.8%, higher than the corresponding average rate in EPELI (2%). We assume that the open-endedness of EPELI, together with the richer context and semantically meaningful block-wise scenarios as compared to classical PM tasks, trigger the use of

strategies that involve manipulation of to-be-remembered information, rather than task maintenance by simple rehearsal. In other words, task characteristics play a considerable role in the repertoire of self-generated strategies that a given task elicits (see also Morrison et al., 2016).

The interest in probing possible strategy evolvment over the single-session testing with EPELI stems from recent empirical evidence that indicates fast changes in strategy use in experimental working memory and episodic memory tasks (Waris, Fellman, et al., 2021; Waris, Jylkkä, et al. 2021). More specifically, these two studies found that increases in strategy use and changes in self-reported strategy were most common in the initial task block transitions. These findings were interpreted in the context of the cognitive skill learning framework (e.g., Chein & Schneider, 2012): with complex tasks, the metacognitive system is initially engaged in generating strategies to handle the task. The block-wise findings from EPELI did not show any systematic changes in the proportion of participants employing a strategy, but block-by-block transitions suggested a similar decreasing trend in strategy changers as Waris and colleagues (Waris, Fellman, et al., 2021; Waris, Jylkkä, et al. 2021) found in their studies. This hints at a gradual stabilization in strategy employment within the single EPELI test session, suggesting that this pattern holds also for a complex PM task. Gradual changes in self-reported PM strategy use, with overall increase in strategy use and more frequent employment of strategies deemed as more effective, have been reported earlier but the time span was very different, a four-week training period with an adaptive PM task (Rose et al., 2015).

Possible convergence in strategy use between different memory tasks relates to the more general issue of determinants of strategy employment. In case individuals vary in their overall degree of strategy proneness, strategy use across tasks should show a positive correlation. We found some evidence for this in the form of a positive association in strategy use between EPELI and Word List Learning, an experimental episodic-verbal memory task. However, this association was rather weak, which could suggest that the decision to use vs. not to use a strategy reflects a complex interplay of task features and participant characteristics. Potentially relevant characteristics in this respect include general cognitive ability (Pizzonia & Suhr, 2022) and metacognitive features such as one's self-efficacy and control beliefs (Hutchens et al., 2013). Finally, one could note that the lack of

correlations with the EPELI Instruction Recall task may have been due to the minimal range (0 or 1) of the variable in question.

4.1. Limitations

There are certain limitations to the present study that should be considered. First, as strategy data stems from verbal self-reports to a general open-ended question, we cannot be sure that all strategies employed were reported. There is previous evidence suggesting that open-ended questions may overestimate the proportion of no strategy users that was quite high (on average 55%) in the present study. Waris, Jylkkä, et al. (2021; see Table 8) administered both an open-ended strategy question and a list-based strategy question after the last block of an adaptive working memory task. The open-ended question yielded 32% of no strategy users, while for the immediately following list-based strategy report that concerned the same task block, only 7% of the same participants chose the “no strategy” alternative. Nevertheless, the fact that reported strategy use was strongly related to EPELI performance supports the conclusion that open-ended strategy reports can catch a significant part of actual strategy use. EPELI raw data including each mouse click and movement could give an opportunity to objectively verify some reported strategy types, such as executing the tasks in a certain room order. We are currently looking into this in another study. Second, as the block-wise strategy reports were retrospective, planning and execution stages cannot be separated here (see, Kliegel et al., 2000). For future studies, it would be possible to insert a planning stage with an explicit report between the task instructions and actual EPELI performance. Third, as noted above, comparisons with studies employing classical PM tasks are complicated by the fact that the current EPELI version differs from them by consisting mostly of shopping list type tasks. While this makes the comparison between EPELI and more traditional time-based or event-based PM less straightforward, we would argue that various to-do-lists with multiple steps of action are relevant for PM research, as they are not uncommon in everyday life. Fourth, as this was an online study, we had not control over the conditions under which the participants performed the tasks, albeit the need for a quiet space was emphasized. Nevertheless, the exclusion criteria and removal of outliers should have helped to counteract this potential problem. Moreover, research indicates that online testing successfully replicates the cognitive task effects observed in the lab (e.g., Enochson & Culbertson, 2015; Germine et al.,

2012; Waris et al., 2017). Also for PM tasks, there is evidence for a comparable performance at laboratory and at home (Zuber et al., 2022). Fifth, it is important to point out that the present evidence for the link between strategy use and EPELI performance is correlative. However, numerous intervention studies on PM strategy training and its effect on task performance have indicated a causal relationship between strategy use and PM performance (for a meta-analysis, see Jones et al., 2021).

4.2. Implications

What are the implications of the present results concerning everyday PM? It seems evident that despite EPELI's apparent verisimilitude, the present simulated everyday task lists given in a testing context differ from daily life. In the latter case, the surroundings are most often very familiar and richer and more dynamic, PM tasks are more varied in terms of contents, priority, time span and environmental cues, both external and internal strategies are in use, and goals are most often set by the individual. Moreover, in everyday life PM task performance does not take place in a testing situation which may bring up maximal rather than typical performance (e.g., Toplak et al., 2013). Instead, we would argue that the present results give insight into the potential for everyday internal PM strategy use in adults by revealing the variety of strategy types (the most common ones here being grouping, action schema utilization, condensing information) that they can generate by themselves when faced with life-like tasks that call for PM and executive performance. This information on naturally occurring strategies should also be helpful when planning further PM interventions that incorporate strategy training.

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Supplementary 1. The memory strategy coding scheme

GENERAL INSTRUCTIONS FOR CODING PARTICIPANTS' OPEN-ENDED BLOCK-WISE MEMORY STRATEGY DESCRIPTIONS IN THE ADULT EPELI EXPERIMENT

- For each strategy description, code three variables: the first reported strategy type (there can be only one primary strategy), the total number of strategy types reported, and the total number of specific strategy details given (be they for one or more strategy types).
- If the strategy description field is completely empty, do not code anything.
- If the participant has typed in “None” but nevertheless given a subsequent description of a strategy, evaluate the response from the strategy description.
- If the participant refers to a strategy s/he used in a previous task block, evaluate the response from the strategy description for that other block.
- If the participant refers to a strategy s/he used for another block that cannot be identified on the basis of the response, mark this as “other strategy”.
- Extraneous information not related to strategy use such as “it went bad”, “the task was difficult”, “my mom disturbed me during task performance” should not be taken into account when rating the strategy descriptions, neither comments that merely describe the sequence of actions one took when performing the task block, or comments that merely recount the task characteristics or the task instructions. Keep in mind that strategy is an identifiable, self-generated way or ways of managing a memory task, thus requiring activity from the part of the participant.
- Possible use of external aids (e.g., “wrote down what needed to be done”) are coded as 999, as these participants will be discarded from the strategy analyses
- The same coding schema for strategy type and strategy level of detail is used for all three tasks where strategy report is collected, namely the EPELI task (10 blocks, strategy report for each block), the EPELI Instruction Recall task (1 block), and the Word List Learning task (3 blocks). Note however that not all strategy types are used in coding all these three tasks.

Code for strategy type	Type	Examples for EPELI	Examples for Word List Learning
0	<p>No explicit strategy use</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No strategy - No clear evidence of strategy use - Repetition of instructions or own action sequence - Response unrelated to strategy use, comments on understanding instructions, or comments on task difficulty - Guessing, intuition, instinct, familiarity, 'gut feeling' 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "No", "None" • "Most of the tasks I remembered, had actually only trouble in remembering to drink the glass of milk" • "At first I made the bed, then put on clothes, drank coffee, ate sandwich and finally moved to the study to turn on the lights but the time ran out." • "This one was hard, I got distracted" • "Followed the same order as was given in the instructions" • "Just guessed and clicked on many things" • "Used my memory" • "By trial and error" • "I listened very carefully" • Only "Yes" or "I used a strategy" or "Attempted to use a mnemonic" (with no description as to what the strategy/mnemonics would have been) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "No system" • "I tried" • "I tried to keep up with the list but found it quite difficult" • "Just tried to concentrate on the words" • "I memorized the words mentally" • "I memorized all the words" • "Tried to apply a strategy/mnemonic"(with no description as to what the strategy/mnemonics would have been)
1	<p>Rehearsal / Repetition</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Rehearsing items verbally, nonverbally or visuomotorically - <i>E.g. repeating, speaking in head, saying in mind, yelling the tasks, rehearsing quietly</i> 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "Memorized the instructions by going through them silently in my mind" • "Rehearsed the tasks in my mind" • "Said out aloud all the instructions" 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "I repeated the words" • "I rehearsed the words in my mind" • "Said aloud all the items in the list in order to keep them in memory"
2	<p>Grouping</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Grouping items together - <i>E.g. chunking, pairing, memorizing in groups, remembering in chunks, thinking in pairs, dividing into subsets, subdividing into sets, splitting into shorter sequences</i> 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "I memorized what I had to do in each room, starting with the bedroom" • "Remembered the tasks room by room" • "Tried to group tasks by their location" • "Grouping tasks by their type, like handling foodstuff or cleaning-related chores" 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "I memorized the words in chunks" • "I grouped the words in pairs" • "I remembered the words in groups" • "grouped together in my mind words that rhymed"
3	<p>Action schema utilization</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>E.g. thinking what one would do at home, thinking of normal household chores, reflecting on what one would do in a similar scenario</i> 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "I tried to think what I usually do before leaving for work" • "These made much sense as they reminded me of things I would do when cleaning the house" • "I do these morning chores every day so it was easy to remember" • "Applied logic based on my own routines" 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • N/A

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> “Followed my standard routine” 	
4	Association - Associating the objects/actions with something outside the stimuli	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> “Associated each task with a letter and then memorized that letter sequence” “Thought of different colors to which I associated the tasks” 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> “I tried to associate each word with something that I have at home”
5	Visualization of objects and/or locations - Linking tasks with some visual/visuospatial representations in mind - <i>E.g. visualizing objects in mind, forming spatial images, visualizing objects in their locations</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> “I tried to see the relevant objects in my mind” “Attempted to visualize the objects and what I was supposed to do with them” “Tried to see myself going through the apartment and doing the things I was supposed to do” “Imagined in my mind how I would do the tasks” “Pictured the tasks in my head” 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> “Built a mental image of the words in my mind” “Visualized the words as they were shown” “I was picturing the words in my head”
6	Condensing information - Abridging the instructions e.g. into keywords	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> “I created just one key word for each task” “Memorized only the crucial contents of the tasks, not the whole sentence” 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> N/A
7	Selective focus - Focusing on only some of the tasks or keywords for the tasks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> “I focused on remembering only a subset of the items and disregarded the rest” “This was difficult, I just concentrated on the easy tasks” “Fixated only on the first 4 tasks” 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> “I focused on remembering only a subset of the words and disregarded the rest” “Just concentrated on the easy words as the task was quite difficult” “Focused on the words I had previously forgotten” “Fixated only on the first 4 words”
8	External cueing - Using objects in the apartment as memory/action triggers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> “My memory failed so I resorted to using the things in the apartment as prompts” “Walked around and looked at various things that reminded me of the tasks I had to do” “Some visual clues like seeing the teddy bear helped to trigger my memory” “Looked for visual reminders in the rooms” 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> N/A
9	Other strategy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> “I put the actions I was supposed to do in a storyline” “Made up a song based on the instructions” “Employed an elimination strategy” 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> “Made up a story based on the words to remember them better” “I tried to match the words to those I saw previously”

		<ul style="list-style-type: none">• “Started with the task that was most difficult to remember”• “Made a list of hierarchies in my mind”	
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Code for strategy level of detail	Level	Examples for EPELI	Examples for Word List Learning
0	No strategy use No strategy use Vague comments that do not point to an identifiable strategy	“No system” “I tried” “I tried to keep up but found it quite difficult” “Just tried to concentrate on the instructions” “I memorized the tasks mentally” “I memorized all the instructions” “Tried to apply a strategy/mnemonic”	“No system” “I tried” “I tried to keep up but found it quite difficult” “Just tried to concentrate on the words” “I memorized the words mentally” “I memorized all the words” “Tried to apply a strategy/mnemonic”
0	An identifiable strategy or strategies without any specific detail	“Grouped the tasks to help to remember them” (<i>grouping</i>) “I rehearsed the tasks” (<i>rehearsal</i>) “I repeated the instructions as they came, and then divided them into groups” (<i>rehearsal, grouping</i>)	“Grouped the words to help to remember them” (<i>grouping</i>) “I rehearsed the words” (<i>rehearsal</i>) “I repeated the words as they came, and then divided them into groups” (<i>rehearsal, grouping</i>)
1	An identifiable strategy or strategies with one specific feature in total	“I tried to remember the tasks in groups of 3 actions” (<i>grouping/groups of 3</i>) “Related the tasks to my own morning routines like washing my face after waking up” (<i>internal cueing/face washing</i>) “Did room by room, starting from the nearest room” (<i>grouping/start room</i>) “I repeated the tasks silently in my mind and then memorized by grouping them room by room like doing the kitchen tasks first” (<i>rehearsal, grouping/kitchen</i>)	“I tried to remember the words in groups of 3” (<i>grouping/groups of 3</i>) “I repeated the words silently in my mind and then memorized by associating them with something, like apple – eating a delicious apple pie” (<i>rehearsal, association/apple</i>)
2	An identifiable strategy or strategies with two specific features in total	“I grouped the tasks room by room and started from the bedroom then the kitchen” (<i>grouping/bedroom, kitchen</i>) “I visualized the tasks like seeing myself driving the exercise bike and used also keywords like ‘wash’ to remember” (<i>visualization/driving exercise bike, keywords/wash</i>)	“I created images in my mind, like a cat on the sofa and a king in a castle” (<i>association/2 examples</i>) “Focused on the words I forgot on the last round and made links between them, like the cat hopping on the king and the eagle landing on a mountain” (<i>selective focus, association/2 examples</i>)
3	An identifiable strategy or strategies with at least three specific features in total	“I associated the tasks with each other, like tooth-brushing – hand washing, placing a book and a magazine in the right place, eating a sandwich while having a cup of tea” (<i>association/3 specific examples</i>) “This was a difficult one -- I focused on only the four last tasks and grouped them by the rooms: things to do in the kitchen and the living room” (<i>selective focus/four last tasks, grouping/2 specific examples</i>)	I linked the words with familiar places, like chair – my favourite armchair in our livingroom, mountain – Mt Snowdon in Wales, castle – the Windsor castle (<i>association/ 3 examples</i>)

4-	...and so on		
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Supplementary Table 2. Number and percentage of strategy use

Strategy type	Block									
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
	25							25	11	
Action schema utilization	(12.4%)	11 (5.4%)	11 (5.4%)	7 (3.5%)	9 (4.5%)	12 (5.9%)	7 (3.5%)	(12.4%)	(5.4%)	3 (1.5%)
Association	0 (0%)	1 (0.5%)	1 (0.5%)	2 (1%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
			25						16	
Condensing information	10 (5%)	14 (6.9%)	(12.4%)	20 (9.9%)	17 (8.4%)	11 (5.4%)	15 (7.4%)	14 (6.9%)	(7.9%)	13 (6.4%)
External cueing	3 (1.5%)	0 (0%)	8 (4%)	5 (2.5%)	5 (2.5%)	2 (1%)	3 (1.5%)	3 (1.5%)	5 (2.5%)	5 (2.5%)
	27	34			44	45	43	28	38	33
Grouping	(13.4%)	(16.8%)	17 (8.4%)	47 (23.3%)	(21.8%)	(22.3%)	(21.3%)	(13.9%)	(18.8%)	(16.3%)
	117	113	122	104		106			111	129
No explicit strategy use	(57.9%)	(55.9%)	(60.4%)	(51.5%)	95 (47%)	(52.5%)	107 (53%)	111 (55%)	(55%)	(63.9%)
Other strategy	8 (4%)	10 (5%)	6 (3%)	5 (2.5%)	17 (8.4%)	8 (4%)	14 (6.9%)	9 (4.5%)	7 (3.5%)	8 (4%)
Rehearsal/Repetition	0 (0%)	6 (3%)	5 (2.5%)	3 (1.5%)	5 (2.5%)	5 (2.5%)	5 (2.5%)	3 (1.5%)	6 (3%)	2 (1%)
Selective focus	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	2 (1%)	2 (1%)	0 (0%)	3 (1.5%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	1 (0.5%)	2 (1%)
Visualization of objects and/or locations	12 (5.9%)	13 (6.4%)	5 (2.5%)	7 (3.5%)	10 (5%)	10 (5%)	8 (4%)	9 (4.5%)	7 (3.5%)	7 (3.5%)

Note. Numbers outside from parentheses shows actual n, and numbers within parentheses the percentage of the total in a given block. N = 202